

Leadership Behavior and Education Supervision Behavior of the Elementary School Principals in Jember Regency and their Effects on the Elementary Teachers' Professional Attitude, Teacher Work Motivation and Teacher Work Satisfaction

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Abstract:- This research was conducted to know whether leadership behavior and education supervision behavior of the elementary school principals in Jember, being together or separated, affected the elementary teachers' professional attitude, work motivation, and work satisfaction. To gain the objective of the research, Ex-post facto research design was applied by involving 50 elementary school principals and 100 elementary school teachers, from 50 elementary schools, as the research subjects. There were five kinds of questionnaire to collect the data about leadership behavior, education supervision behavior, professional attitude, work motivation, and work satisfaction. The collected data were analyzed by applying multiple regression. From the analyses, it was found that leadership behavior and education supervision behavior of the elementary school principals, being together or separated, significantly affected the elementary school teachers' professional attitude, work motivation, and work satisfaction.

Keywords:- leadership behavior, education supervision behavior, professional attitude, work motivation, and work satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

The research problem was related to the leadership behavior and education supervision behavior of the elementary school principals and their effects on the elementary teachers' professional attitude, work motivation and work satisfaction in Jember. At the moment, there is no ideal and effective leadership behavior and education supervision behavior done by the elementary school principals, which can increase their teachers' participation, professional attitude, work motivation and work satisfaction. Most of School management books, especially for the elementary school level, do not provide a specific guideline of leadership, and a clear guideline of education supervision. They only give administrative guideline. Although the guideline of education supervision, is provided, but it is difficult to be applied, because it is too theoretical and it is not appropriate for the school's real needs. In other words, the education supervision guideline is less contextual and

less functional so that it can give less effects on the improvement of teachers' professional skills, work motivation and work satisfaction.

Therefore, the elementary school principals' leadership behavior and education supervision behavior are needed to be effective. Having the elementary school principals' effective leadership behavior and effective education supervision behavior, it is expected that elementary school teachers' professionalism skills, work motivation, and work satisfaction can be improved. The improvement of teachers' professionalism, work motivation, and work satisfaction hopefully can give a positive effect on the improvement of education quality at elementary schools.

To increase teachers' professionalism skills, work motivation, and work satisfaction, needs contextual, democratic and accommodative leadership behavior, and education supervision behavior of the elementary school principals (Masyhud, 2021). In addition, a clear and operational guideline of leadership implementation and education supervision is needed (Masyhud, 2017). In order to have such a clear and operational guideline, complete and valid data are required. Therefore, this research was needed to be conducted.

The previous related study conducted in Jember, East Java, Indonesia, found that the elementary school principals' leadership behavior had affected 92.97% on the teachers' work motivation, and 75.78% on work satisfaction (Masyhud, et al, 2022). Dealing with leadership style, the elementary school principals in Jember had some various leadership styles, covering otoriter leadership style (32.01%), democratic leadership style (22.10%), leaderships do democratic style (19.15%) and the rest in about 26.76% had laissezfaire leadership style (Masyhud, 2017). Whatever the leadership styles applied by the elementary school principals in Jember, most of them (73.64 %) did not understand well about their role as leaders in education. Furthermore, the research found that most of them (76.5%) imitated the leadership style applied by the previous elementary school principals. In addition, 11.5% of them used the leadership style based on the books they had read, and the rest (12 %)

used the leadership style of whatever they can do (Masyhud, 2019).

Another related research found that 57.08% of the elementary school principals in Jember applied Top-down education supervision model, 22.55% applied collaborative supervision model, and the rest (20.37%) did not do supervision because they did not understand well about what they should do as an education supervisor (Masyhud, 2018).

Based on the ideas and the research findings above, the research problems were formulated as the following: Did the leadership behavior and education supervision behavior of the elementary school principals in Jember affect the elementary teachers' professional attitude, work motivation, and work satisfaction? If yes, how far was the effect?

The research problems can be stated operationally as the following.

- Did leadership behavior (X_1) and education supervision behavior (X_2) of the elementary school principals in Jember, being together, affect the elementary teachers' professional attitude (Y_1), teachers' work motivation (Y_2), and work satisfaction (Y_3)? If yes, how far was the effect?
- Did the leadership behavior (X_1) and education supervision behavior (X_2) of the elementary school principals in Jember, being separated, affect the elementary teachers' professional attitude (Y_1), work motivation (Y_2), and work satisfaction (Y_3)? If yes, how far was the effect for each variable consisting of the elementary teachers' professional attitude, work motivation, and work satisfaction?

II. RESEARCH METHOD

The research design used in this research was Ex-post Facto Research (Kerlinger, 2019; Masyhud, 2021). The research design was implemented by applying the Cross-sectional Survey approach (Masyhud, 2021). Ex-post Facto Research design was selected because it is very appropriate with this research characteristics which revealed the fact that had already happened while this research was conducted. The leadership behavior and education supervision behavior under investigation had been being implemented by the elementary school principals in Jember. In addition, professional attitude, work motivation, and work satisfaction were also performed by the elementary school teachers under the principals' leadership behavior. In this research, all the facts were re-uncovered in order to analyze the relationship between work atmosphere, created by the elementary school principals, consisting of leadership behavior and education supervision behavior applied by the elementary school principals, and the teachers' behavior dealing with their professional attitude, work motivation, and work satisfaction which were caused by the elementary school principals' leadership behavior and education supervision behavior.

Survey Cross-sectional approach was used because the research subjects were in a great number and the data needed were also great, whereas the time available and the budget were limited. In addition, this approach can be used

to collect the data needed comprehensively in a relatively short time.

Moreover, purposive method was used to choose Jember regency as the research area. All the elementary school principals and the elementary school teachers in Jember are the population of the research. The sample of the research was 50 elementary school principals and 100 elementary school teachers taken from the 50 elementary schools by using Proportional Quota Random Sampling. The data needed were collected by using a questionnaire. There were five kinds of a questionnaire used in this research, a questionnaire for the principals' leadership behavior, a questionnaire for the principals' education supervision behavior, a questionnaire for the teachers' professional attitude, a questionnaire for the teachers' work motivation, and a questionnaire for the teachers' work satisfaction. After all the data were collected, Multiple regression and Product moment correlation by using SPSS version 26 were used to analyze the collected data. Above all, this research was conducted in 7 months.

III. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research results can be classified into three sections based on the research hypotheses type as the following.

A. *The Effect of the Principal's Leadership Behavior (X_1), the Principal's Education Supervision Behavior (X_2) on the Teacher's Professional Attitude (Y_1)*

There were three hypotheses tested in this stage: (a) being together, all the independent variables consisting of the principal's leadership behavior (X_1), the principal's education supervision behavior (X_2) affected significantly on the teacher's professional attitude (Y_1); (b) there was correlation between the principal's leadership behavior (X_1) and the teacher's professional attitude (Y_1); (c) there was correlation between the principal's education supervision behavior (X_2) and the teacher's professional attitude (Y_1).

In addition, the analysis results of Multiple Regression by using SPSS dealing with the elementary school principal's leadership behavior and education supervision behavior on the elementary school teachers' professional attitude showed multiple regression coefficients as the following: $a_1 = 0.221671$, $a_2 = 0.095182$ with constant number of 42.054580. From the results, the regression equation was: $Y = 0.221671X_1 + 0.095182X_2 + 42.054580$. Furthermore, the Standard Error of the regression equation was 11.130., and its Multiple regression was 0.766. The determinant coefficient (R-Square) Regression equation was 0.587. The value of F-reg for the regression equation was 33.413. In order that the Regression equation can be used to test the hypothesis, it should have two requirements: F-reg value should be significant and the regression equation must be linear.

The analysis results found that F-reg value was greater than the one in significant level of 0.05 with db 2.47 showing 3.15. So, F-reg value was greater than the one in F-table ($F > 0.05$). Therefore, it can be concluded that regression equation result was significant.

After that, the linearity test was conducted by finding out the galat variance estimation of Y on X, then comparing the average of squared sum for the residu. If the variants was smaller or the same with the squared sum of the residu, it means that multiple regression equation was linear. However, if the variants was greater than the squared sum for the residu, it means that multiple regression equation was non linear. From the data analysis done previously, it was found that the Standard Error was 11.130, and after being squared the result was 123.87. It was the same as the average of squared sum for the residu. That was 123.87. Therefore, it can be concluded that the multiple regression equation was linear.

The results of the two tests showed that multiple regression equation results had already fulfilled the requirements to predict the effect of each independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y), meaning the requirements to test the research hypothesis were also fulfilled.

To test the first hypothesis, the result of multiple regression analysis was used as the basis. Whether the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted or rejected based on the following: If multiple correlation (R) result is positive and greater than zero, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, so the alternate hypothesis (H_1) is accepted. On the other hand, if multiple correlation (R) result is negative or zero, the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted, and the alternate hypothesis (H_1) is rejected.

From the analysis result, it was found that multiple correlation (R) was 0.766 which was greater than zero (null), meaning the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected ($R > 0$). Therefore, the alternate hypothesis (H_1) saying that all the independent variables, leadership behavior, education supervision behavior done by the elementary school principals, being together, affected the elementary school teachers' professional attitude in Jember regency.

In addition, the effect of leadership behavior and supervision behavior on teacher's professional attitude was 58.709% which was found by squaring multiple correlation (R). This result showed that 58.709% of the elementary school teachers' professional attitude in Jember regency was affected by leadership behavior and education supervision behavior, being together, done by the elementary school principals.

Based on the result, it can be said that 41.291% of the elementary school teachers' professional attitude was affected by other variables which were not investigated in this research. The possible variables were IQ, motivation being a teacher, working environment, working facilities and welfare. Hence, it was needed to conduct further research on the effect of those other variables on the elementary school teachers' professional attitude.

Furthermore, to know the effect of each variable separately can be found from the correlation results analysis, as the following. The correlation between leadership behavior (X_1) and education supervision behavior (X_2), done by the elementary school principals,

and the elementary school teachers' professional attitude (Y_1), being separatedly, were 0.755 and 0.516. Those results were greater than the value in R table with df.49 in 95% significant level showing 0.279. Therefore, it can be said that the two variables, leadership behavior and education supervision behavior done by the elementary school principals, were the real predictor of the teachers' professional attitude establishment.

Hence, the contribution of each independent variable on the teachers' professional attitude establishment from the total contribution of 58.709% can be separated as the following: 50.576 % for the leadership behavior, and 8.033% for the education supervision behavior.

B. *The Effect of the Principal's Leadership Behavior (X_1), the Principal's Education Supervision Behavior (X_2) on the Teacher's Work Motivation (Y_2)*

There were three hypotheses tested in this stage: a) being together, all the independent variables consisting the principal's leadership behavior (X_1), the principal's education supervision behavior (X_2) affected significantly the teacher's work motivation (Y_2); b) there was a correlation between the principal's leadership behavior (X_1) and the teacher's work motivation (Y_1); c) there was a correlation between the principal's education supervision behavior (X_2) and the teacher's work motivation (Y_2).

In addition, the analysis results of Multiple Regression by using SPSS dealing with the elementary school principal's leadership behavior and education supervision behavior on the elementary school teachers' work motivation showed multiple regression coefficients as the following: $a_1 = 0.207605$, $a_2 = 0.119531$ with constant number of 37.908410. From the results, the regression equation was: $Y = 0.207605X_1 + 0.119531X_2 + 37.908410$. Furthermore, the Standard Error of the regression equation was 12.759; and its Multiple regression was 0.714. The determinant coefficient (R-Square) Regression equation was 0.510. In order that the Regression equation can be used to test the hypothesis, it should have two requirements: F-reg value should be significant and the regression equation must be linear.

The analysis results found that F-reg value was 24.488. It was greater than the one in significant level of 0.05 with df 2.47 showing 3.15. So, F-reg value was greater than the one in F-table ($F > 0.05$). Therefore, it can be concluded that regression equation result was significant.

After that, the linearity test was conducted by finding out the galat variance estimation of Y on X, then comparing the average of squared sum for the residu. If the variants was smaller or the same with the squared sum of the residu, it means that multiple regression equation was linear. However, if the variants was greater than the squared sum for the residu, it means that multiple regression equation was non linear. From the data analysis done previously, it was found that the Standard Error was 12.759, and after being squared the result was 162.790. It was the same as the average of squared sum for the residu. That was 162.790. Therefore, it can be concluded that the multiple regression equation was linear.

The results of the two tests showed that multiple regression equation results had already fulfilled the requirements to predict the effect of each independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y), meaning the requirements to test the research hypothesis were also fulfilled.

To test the first hypothesis, the result of multiple regression analysis was used as the basis. Whether the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted or rejected based on the following: If multiple correlation (R) result is positive and greater than zero, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, so the alternate hypothesis (H_1) is accepted. On the other hand, if multiple correlation (R) result is negative or zero, the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted, and the alternate hypothesis (H_1) is rejected.

From the analysis result, it was found that multiple correlation (R) was 0.714 which was greater than zero (null), meaning the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected ($R > 0$). Therefore, the alternate hypothesis (H_1) saying that all the independent variables, leadership behavior (X_1), education supervision behavior (X_2) done by the elementary school principals, being together, affected the elementary school teachers' work motivation (Y_2) in Jember regency.

In addition, the effect of leadership behavior and supervision behavior on teacher's work motivation was 51.030% which was found by squaring multiple correlation (R). This result showed that 51.030% of the elementary school teachers' work motivation in Jember regency was affected by leadership behavior and education supervision behavior, being together, done by the elementary school principals.

Based on the result, it can be said that 48.97% of the elementary school teachers' work motivation was affected by other variables which were not investigated in this research. The possible variables were salary/welfare, work complexity, achievement level in doing the job, motivation to be a teacher, working environment, working facilities and institution management. Hence, it was needed to conduct further research on the effect of those other variables on the elementary school teachers' work motivation.

Furthermore, to know the effect of each variable separately can be found from the correlation analysis results, as the following. The correlation between leadership behavior (X_1) and education supervision behavior (X_2), done by the elementary school principals, and the elementary school teachers' work motivation (Y_2), being separately, were 0.697 and 0.506. Those results were greater than the value in R table with df.49 in 95% significant level showing 0.279. Therefore, it can be said that the two variables, leadership behavior and education supervision behavior done by the elementary school principals, were the real predictor of the elementary teachers' work motivation establishment.

Hence, the contribution of each independent variable on the teachers' work motivation establishment from the total contribution of 51.030% can be separated as the following:

- 41.627 % for the elementary school principal's leadership behavior
- 9.403% for the elementary school principal's supervision behavior.

C. The Effect of the Principal's Leadership Behavior (X_1), the Principal's Education Supervision Behavior (X_2) on the Teacher's Work Satisfaction (Y_3)

There were three hypotheses tested in this stage: a) being together, all the independent variables consisting the principal's leadership behavior (X_1), the principal's education supervision behavior (X_2) affected significantly the teacher's work satisfaction (Y_3); b) there was a correlation between the principal's leadership behavior (X_1) and the teacher's work motivation (Y_3); c) there was a correlation between the principal's education supervision behavior (X_2) and the teacher's work satisfaction (Y_3).

In addition, the analysis results of Multiple Regression by using SPSS dealing with the elementary school principal's leadership behavior and education supervision behavior on the elementary school teachers' work satisfaction showed multiple regression coefficients as the following: $a_1 = 0.202420$, $a_2 = 0.131720$ with constant number of 37.318650. From the results, the regression equation was: $Y = 0.202420X_1 + 0.131720X_2 + 37.318650$. Furthermore, the Standard Error of the regression equation was 12.774; and its Multiple regression was 0.713. The determinant coefficient (R-Square) Regression equation was 0.509. In order that the Regression equation can be used to test the hypothesis, it should have two requirements: F-reg value should be significant and the regression equation must be linear.

The analysis results found that F-reg value was 24.366. It was greater than the one in F-table with a significant level of 0.05 and df of 2.47 showing 3.15. So, F-reg value was greater than the one in F-table ($F > 0.05$). Therefore, it can be concluded that regression equation result was significant.

After that, the linearity test was conducted by finding out the galat variance estimation of Y on X, then comparing the average of squared sum for the residu. If the variants was smaller or the same with the squared sum of the residu, it means that multiple regression equation was linear. However, if the variants was greater than the squared sum for the residu, it means that multiple regression equation was non linear. From the data analysis done previously, it was found that the Standard Error was 12.774, and after being squared the result was 163.175. It was the same as the average of squared sum for the residu. That was 163.175. Therefore, it can be concluded that the multiple regression equation was linear.

The results of the two tests showed that multiple regression equation results had already fulfilled the requirements to predict the effect of each independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y), meaning the

requirements to test the research hypothesis were also fulfilled.

To test the first hypothesis, the result of multiple regression analysis was used as the basis. Whether the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted or rejected based on the following: If multiple correlation (R) result is positive and greater than zero, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, so the alternate hypothesis (H_1) is accepted. On the other hand, if multiple correlation (R) result is negative or zero, the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted, and the alternate hypothesis (H_1) is rejected.

From the analysis result, it was found that multiple correlation (R) was 0.714 which was greater than zero (null), meaning the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected ($R > 0$). Therefore, the alternate hypothesis (H_1) saying that all the independent variables, leadership behavior (X_1), education supervision behavior (X_2) done by the elementary school principals, being together, affected the elementary school teachers' work satisfaction (Y_3) in Jember regency.

In addition, the effect of leadership behavior and supervision behavior on teacher's work satisfaction was 50.905% which was found by squaring multiple correlation (R). This result showed that 50.905% of the elementary school teachers' work satisfaction in Jember regency was affected by leadership behavior and education supervision behavior, being together, done by the elementary school principals.

Based on the result, it can be said that 49.095% of the elementary school teachers' work satisfaction was affected by other variables which were not investigated in this research. The possible variables were salary/welfare, work complexity, achievement level in doing the job, involvement in making decision, working environment, working facilities and institution management. Hence, it was needed to conduct further research on the effect of those other variables on the elementary school teachers' work satisfaction.

Furthermore, to know the effect of each variable separately can be found from the correlation analysis results, as the following. The correlation between leadership behavior (X_1) and education supervision behavior (X_2), done by the elementary school principals, and the elementary school teachers' work satisfaction (Y_3), being separately, were 0.692 and 0.527. Those results were greater than the value in R table with db.49 in 95% significant level showing 0.279. Therefore, it can be said that the two variables, leadership behavior and education supervision behavior done by the elementary school principals, were the real predictor of the elementary teachers' work satisfaction establishment.

Hence, the contribution of each independent variable on the teachers' work satisfaction establishment from the total contribution of 51.030% can be separated as the following:

- 40.318 % for the elementary school principal's leadership behavior

- 10.587% for the elementary school principal's supervision behavior.

IV. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Conclusion

Based on the data analysis, hypothesis verification and the discussion about the research results, it could be concluded that being together and being separated all the independent variables consisting of leadership behavior and education supervision behavior done by the elementary school principals in Jember regency affected the elementary teachers' professional attitude, work motivation, and work satisfaction. The effects tended to be positive because the correlation between the two independent variables, leadership behavior and education supervision behavior done by the elementary school principals, and the elementary teachers' professional attitude, work motivation, and work satisfaction was positive and significant with the result of 56.709%, 51.030%, and 56.709% for each respectively. In addition, leadership behavior done by the elementary school principal tended to have far greater effect than education supervision behavior done on the elementary teachers' professional attitude, work motivation, and work satisfaction.

Suggestion

Based on the research results, there are some points suggested to the following people. Firstly, the head of education office in Jember suggested to give intensive training to the elementary school principals about leadership behavior, because it was proved that leadership behavior could give very good significant contribution on the teachers, professional attitude, work motivation, and work satisfaction. In order that to get maximum results, it can be done by making collaboration with higher education institutions nearby. Secondly, other researchers, especially who have interest on, leadership and education supervision at elementary schools, are suggested to use this research results as the basis to conduct further similar research in the future.

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